

A troubled strangeness in Daniel Zea's work

by Mauricio Carrasco

"It doesn't interest me where or what or with whom you have studied.

I want to know what sustains you from the inside, when all else falls away."

The Invitation, inspired by Oriah Mountain Dreamer, Native American Elder, May 1994.

Recently, I submitted a paper to a prestigious journal. With a certain degree of hope and secretly slightly proud of myself, I felt quite shocked when I received the refusal mail, with the classic phrase '*we had many excellent proposals*'. Discouraged and overwhelmed for the next five to ten minutes, the thoughts that crossed my mind were of the sort of "everything looks full, everywhere seems crowded, every academic position is taken." I remembered Donna Haraway's urge, "make kin, not babies": the Anthropos' waiting list is huge and it doesn't need any more new active members by now (I mean by 'now' my lifetime frame...), with a gentle reminder at the back of my head that "your chances are lesser when you come from the Global South" acting as a self-patronising calming balm against my own fierce self-criticism.

The main argument for the paper's refusal was that I constantly switched from different personas' perspectives throughout the abstract, which included the many actors of the transdisciplinary research proposal, in a sort of academic schizophrenia. I reckon that this article won't be the exception since I no longer conceive of artistic research without a phenomenological component: it is essential to experience in the flesh what is the object of my reflection, *being significant to each other -in specific differences-* as brilliantly put by -again- Haraway.

This last *passage de siècle* saw an emergence of a myriad of composers-sound artists like a *fleshly material-semiotic presence in the body of technoscience* (you guessed right, it's Haraway's!). Daniel sets himself in a posthuman convergence between technology, nature, human and non-human living agents. Through his works, he searches for ways for the human to connect with spirituality. At the same time, he highlights the Anthropos' impossibility of communication among their peers in this high-tech globalised world.

This sort of *cyborgcentrism* emphasises the constitutive aspects and contradictions of us humans – glued to our smartphones and computers, therefore cyborgs: our spirituality and our matter, our immanence and our transcendence, music as the food of the body and the soul. Opposites attract: the accelerationism of highly technologized works where spam texts are triggered by a keyboard in *Borracho Digital* (2019) or by the performers’ faces via a face tracking algorithm in *Swallow* (2019), cede the place to a decelerative introspective new animistic practice in works such as *Waira* (2020) and *Chuma* (2022).

Daniel's "Right to be forgotten"¹ by refusing to adhere to Facebook's dematerialised body data owning, contrasts with the everlasting composers’ wish for historical perpetuation. By putting forward “energising projects that express generative narratives and do not wallow in the rhetoric of crisis” (Braidotti: 2019), the composer actualises the virtual and sublimates it into a creative praxis that takes from dazzling pop references of images, texts and sounds. Zea’s refusal to enter a *game over* aesthetics – that many of those aforementioned pop culture references embrace –, relies instead on hope and trust in working and playing for a resurgent world by building a series of small narratives instead of a larger grandiloquent one.

This preference for pluralistic perspectives, as expressed by Lyotard in *The Postmodern Condition* may explain the apparent contrast between the energetic, highly technologized works and the meditative works that aim for a pastoral care that metaphorically recreates the healing function of shamanistic rituals. The *sympoiesis* that “collectively produces systems that do not have self-defined spatial or temporal boundaries” (Dempster: 1998) of the latter in contrast with the *autopoietic* autonomous unit systems that tend to be monolithically controlled of the former coexist in his body of work.

But how to incorporate ancestral practices, technology, a search for spirituality and a certain flair for new animistic perspectives within an artistic practice presented for an overwhelmingly white Eurocentric audience, avoiding a binary dichotomy between *sympoiesis* and *autopoiesis*? Braidotti warns us that "the simultaneous occurrence of opposite effects defeats the logic of excluded middle and fits in with the manic-depressive alternation of euphoria and melancholia, which is the political economy of affectivity in

¹ “Right to be Forgotten” (RTBF) refers to EU legislation that can be resumed as a right to erasure. In brief, the legislation implies that “natural persons” as “data subjects” have, under certain conditions, the right to ask companies to remove links with personal data about them on the internet.

advanced capitalism." In this globalised era where any utilisation of indigenous and first nations' symbols and rituals can be interpreted as a marketable commodity, Zea's posture identifies with that "all identities are in process and, consequently, are inherently contradictory" (Braidotti: 2012). In parallel, if all technological progress is experienced – by those who have access to it – as an exciting promise of reduction of labour (Ngai: 2020), societal hybridisation requires from us to re-link race, sex, gender, economic classes, geographic origins and species' otherness specificities and differentiations to redress the curse of globalisation.

If we agree that globalised implies marginalised, we would have to agree also on the existence of whom Deleuze defined as "the missing people," those who appear when we sweep under the societal rug. Since recent scientific scholarship tends to agree that nature is constructed, not discovered, and that truth is made, not found, the future of our artistic practices has epistemic constructive freedom and an ethical endeavour that considers the crowded margins by proposing *alternative modes of becoming*. That's where I locate Daniel's work: its qualitative leap has already been taken through an affirmed embedded supra-disciplinarity. Regarding the "cartographic accuracy, with the corollary of ethical accountability, and the combination of critique with creativity that includes a flair for paradoxes" (Braidotti: 2012), I do think that there is still work to accomplish, in a collaborative path, from the margins' perspective, in perpetual nomadism.

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